

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AND THEIR USE IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract

In the article, the issues of organizing and using electronic courses based on the module technology created on LMS platforms in the educational process, the effectiveness of their use and increasing the effectiveness of education using their capabilities are discussed.

Keywords: electronic course, platform, modular technology, learning objective, didactic materials, educational tools, electronic textbook, interest, theoretical training, practical training.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-60 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" on January 28, 2022, as well as, in order to implement the priority tasks of bringing the sphere of information and communication technologies to a new level, the task of establishing the education of more than 6.5 thousand young people in the sphere of information technologies per year through the development of personnel training activities in the sphere of digital technologies in the form of distance education was defined¹. In this regard, there are many educational platforms for organizing distance learning in educational institutions which are effective in organizing and managing distance learning.

According to pedagogues, if teaching is properly organized on the basis of module technology, students will learn new educational materials, improve their skills and qualifications at any stage of education. The module is formed based on the algorithm and includes components as follows: specific goal, theoretical knowledge, practical training, methodical instructions, control, mastered knowledge, assessment of skills, etc.

The studying in module technology is carried out based on the following sequence:

- analyzing of the initial conditions of modular training;
- preparing of educational didactic materials and teaching applications;
- conducting of theoretical and practical training;
- assessing of theoretical and practical skills of students.

All of the above is aimed at expanding the level of student thinking, determining the cause of events and teaching research.

The main essence of the module system is to provide that students learn the various components of the educational unit in a consistent sequence.

The use of a modular system in education provides an opportunity to quickly develop and apply a new module instead of an old module unit.

The advantage of teaching based on the module system is that more attention is paid to the independent work and self-control of learners.

The duration of training based on the module system depends on the training of the learner and the level of his desire to acquire professional qualifications.

The Analyzing of the initial conditions for the organization of training based on module technology:

Firstly, the level of preparation of students is analyzed, and their knowledge, level and ability of learning educational materials are determined. Because their self-confidence, capability, personal status and age have a certain influence on their education. Based on the classification of students according to their abilities, they are recommended to learn the subject independently.

Secondly, the existing conditions are analyzed. It includes the following aspects[3], [4]:

- Legal conditions. In this, the curriculum and programs related to the educational process will be studied.
- Conditions related to the organization of the educational process. In this, the place and other conditions of the theoretical and practical training included in the module will be analyzed.
- Technical conditions. In this, the state of availability of technical equipment and devices, educational and auxiliary audio-visual tools will be studied.

Thirdly, subjects to be passed are analyzed and various resources necessary for determining the content of the modules (such as, educational materials, etc.), will be studied. For instance, textbooks, manuals and other literature.

The determining of the educational aim and content of the module. In teaching on the basis of module technology, the aim and content of the subject being studied, as well as the aim and content of the modules will be determined. At the end of the educational aims, the knowledge, skills and personal skills that the student should achieve as a result of education are determined. In this case, educational goals are developed based on the standard requirements of network

¹ <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6166539> - O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2022 yil 22 avgustdagi PQ-357-sonli "2022-2023 yillarda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari

sohasini yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi qarori.

education. Modulni o'rganish maqsadi qanchalik aniq bo'lsa, unga erishuvchanlik shunchalik oson bo'ladi. The clearer the learning objective of the module, it will be easier to achieve it.

The preparing of didactic materials and educational tools for the module. The educational didactic materials and educational tools mean that sources of information that serve to form knowledge and skills. In the teaching on the basis of modular technology, textual and visual tools are used as didactic materials in theoretical and practical lessons, such as educational textbook, index cards and lecture texts, handouts, methodological instructional materials.

The conducting theoretical and practical training. It is recommended that to conduct the theoretical training included in the module in the following sequence.

Interest (Motivation). For instance, the lesson begins with an explanation of an interesting discovery, news or services related to the topic.

Giving information (knowledge). The teacher will explain his new materials to the students, gives short lectures, organizes discussions and educational conversations. Before the studying a new module unit, the previous module units are repeated with a brief summary.

Appropriate handouts are provided for the module unit. This makes the learning process easier. Sufficient time will be allocated to distribute and review them one after the other in a modular unit. The tasks are given to strengthen mastery knowledge. Students are given tasks that create an opportunity to think and process information. After each task or exercise, the work is assessed. An open discussion of the results in the group works gives good results. The module must be set as a time for the final conversation at the end.

The assessment of the theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications of students. The knowledge and skills of student should be estimated regularly in accordance with the learning objectives. Assessment is based on legal, pedagogical and psychological principles and state educational standards. The process of studying the entire module and all its components are examined through the assessment. This is determined that the module is yielding or not issuing the expected result.

Thus, all technologies used in pedagogical technology are to learn from teacher and have skills at demand levels. Electronical textbook is an effective training tool that allows the basic principles of the didactic to be reliably and high. The creating of electronical textbook using digital technologies make it easier for

the purpose of achieving the goal. These provide that the flexibility of the context of electronical textbook for different parts of users. It is recommended that to follow the basic principles in the creation of electronical textbook, concentrated didactic, technical, technological, ergonomic, aesthetic and other requirements. The electronical textbook hear the learned material in respect of traditional textbooks and eases understanding through the ways to influence emotional memories, and is adapted to the level of preparation for the needs of recipients. The essence of the electronical textbooks makes complex calculations and substitutions, which attracts attention to a large number of information and assignments and allowing more practical issues, allowing them to solve more practical problems. A wide range of opportunities will be created for self-examination at all stages of learning process. The work will be submitted to beautiful and accurate systematization and it will be submitted to the teacher on a file or paper. It will improve electronical textbooks that proper organization by examination groups, analysis of examination results and making final decisions. It should be noted that courses in the LMS Moodle system as distance education is one of the most important factors in increasing the efficiency of education. If an LMS Moodle course is created in this subject, knowing about this subject through the Internet will great help in learning it.

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